

LIFE PREDICTION FOR AROMATIC POLYAMIDE REINFORCEMENTS

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Introduction

The short-term tensile strength of materials such as Kevlar 49 is known to be remarkably insensitive to local defects and to mechanical abuse. This is a main reason why it is used in both textiles and in certain robust composites, where carbon fibre might otherwise have been adopted. Since the fibre is polymeric, several authors have expressed fears about its long-term degradation at the molecular level. Existing specifications are only concerned with short-term properties.

In order to detect change, the samples chosen must be consistent, and the strength of Kevlar 49 yarn of 1420 denier, from a given spool is indeed consistent, to $\pm 2\%$, which compares favourably with the variability of individual fibres or of composites. This paper first discusses tensile strength and imperfections of the fibres, and observed creep of the yarn. It then relates the form of residual strength curves to the rate of damage growth and shows how stress-rupture curves can plausibly be generated from the change in damage growth rate and the activation energy for stress-free aging. From stress-rupture data at 150 °C, 110 °C and 65 °C the most probable yarn lifetimes are predicted at temperatures between 23 and 200 °C, and stress levels between 10 and 70% of ultimate.

1 Tensile Strength and Imperfections

The properties of aromatic polyamide fibres and their composites are affected by the environment (1) but remain sufficiently attractive for these fibres to be used in the construction of both aircraft and missiles, as well as in more orthodox textiles, ropes and fabrics of low mass and bulk. With hindsight, many of the observed shortcomings of this fibre can be related to its microstructural arrangement. Kevlar 49 fibre has a highly oriented and highly crystalline core, in which the aromatic chains are aligned, in a slightly pleated form, parallel to the fibre axis (2). The chains crystallise out as hydrogen-bonded sheets radiating from that axis, leaving only slightly disordered tie molecules and Van de Waals forces to hold the sheets together in the circumferential direction. Generally the cores have a thin "skin" of more disordered polymer around them which also shows some radial texture.

The manufacturer's specification provides only for a minimum fibre modulus. Batch to batch variations of up to 30% in modulus can be related directly to crystallographic orientation of the core material relative to the fibre axis (3, 4).

Many examples are reported in the literature of this skin peeling easily away from the core and of cores themselves splitting under shear or tension. Indeed split cores are quite common in the unstressed fibre and batches have been seen in which the skin exists only over part of the circumference (4). In spite of this, only small variations are to be found in yarn tensile strength (5), and both yarn strength and fibre strength seem insensitive to microstructure. There is no practical difference in tensile strength with accuracy of orientation and little distinction between for example Kevlar 29 and Kevlar 49.

Compressive failure is initiated in the fibre at low strains ~0.5% by the formation of kink bands, and the fibre may be compressed to several % strain overall, and at least an order greater within each band (6). In spite of this apparently heavy damage, some 90% of tensile strength is retained, as it is in fibres which have been deformed laterally. We have compressed dry yarns held under high tension, using mean compressive loads of the order 1 GPa, without inducing tensile failure. Sufficiently high pressures were generated at line contacts between fibres to leave each fibre with a polygonal rather than a round section. It seems probable that if the lateral order in the fibre cross-section could be made random, rather than radial, the compressive and shear properties would be much improved.

Certainly compressive weakening is easily induced in Kevlar 49. Fibres previously subjected to long-term tensile stress and fibres degraded by solar radiation are less elastic in bending than the pristine fibre; they kink and develop axial cracks more readily. The growth of this class of damage has been observed and reported (7) but given this tendency to decouple one part of a fibre from another, the effect on residual tensile strength is likely to be modest, unless the fibre core were considered to be a loose assemblage of polycrystalline grains, rather than a lateral crystallisation of an already aligned and strong polymeric fibre.

Detachment of the skin from the fibre core is absent in those tensile tests where the fibre is placed in an inert liquid, suppressing the backlash and compression pulse which otherwise detaches the skin after fracture. However, in stress-rupture tests of the yarn the fibre skin is frequently detached locally, most clearly seen in an apparent stress-whitening of local patches, caused by helical springs of skin which break free and stick out from the surface. These patches do not usually become failure sites and there is no detectable jump in the creep curve, suggesting the separation is fairly localised. It is shown below that there is an excess of scatter in rupture life-times of yarns at high stresses, beyond what would be expected from the low yarn variability in the short term, and from the slope of the stress-rupture curve. It is probable, though not certain, that this is related to the extent of skin-core separation, which must ultimately frustrate load-sharing between skin and core, causing the skin to be ruptured first.

2 Creep

We have tried without success to relate observed creep to the type of damage which must develop prior to stress-rupture. Creep measured in yarns over a wide range of stresses and times in dry storage conditions is completely recoverable at equivalent rates and times, apart from that associated with the final fracture of individual fibres, which immediately precedes

Fig 1 Wet creep of untwisted yarn at 20 °C (different stresses)

Fig 2 Exposed at Innisfail

Fig 3 Exposed at Waltham Abbey

Loss of mean strength of yarns in sunlight

stress-rupture (8). Even at ambient temperatures creep needs to be accounted for in design (typical creep is +7% of applied strain in the first 300 sec, then +.02% per decade of time thereafter, almost independent of stress). The insensitivity to stress suggests a tightening of the microstructure with increasing stress, and there is certainly a permanent increase of elastic modulus under load (some 15% in a year) in spite of full recovery of the creep itself (8). This can cause a significant permanent set.

Water penetrates Kevlar fibres easily and quickly. One would expect it to soften any poorly crystallised polymer by swamping both hydrogen bonding and Van de Waals forces, as it does in nylon or cellulose. In the event, the effect on ambient creep is small at most stress levels. There is a temporary increase in ambient rate of creep upon water immersion, but little increase in total creep except at extreme stresses, when an irrecoverable relaxation occurs of the order 0.2%. There is again little change in the residual strength and no further increase in modulus compared with creep loading in the dry state, so we have tended to associate this creep with complete slip between the core and the skin. A more disturbing result has been the observation of similar creep in a length of wet yarn at a low stress (0.1 of UTS) after an induction period of nearly a year (Fig 1). The estimates made by Morgan (9) for the chemical hydrolysis of this fibre by water do not suggest any corresponding effect on residual strength in this timescale, a fact confirmed by tensile tests after prolonged wet storage.

3 Residual Strength in Tension - The Form of the Curves

Stress-rupture data define only the terminations of residual strength curves, when the stress causing the aging becomes equal to the residual strength in the material. If the effect of applied stress is very marked, it causes damage growth and weakening many decades of time sooner than the material would have degraded naturally. We have previously noted the two extremes of shape (10). The "sudden-death" model supposes that after a prolonged induction period depending on the applied stress, there is a sudden drop in strength. This might well be appropriate for materials broken by propagation of a single crack. However, it has been shown that these aromatic fibres are insensitive to local damage of this kind. It is therefore assumed that, as in many composites, final failure is the consequence of a series of small damage events.

The other extreme assumption is one of damage random in position and increasing only linearly with time. The effect of this is less sudden ie an order of magnitude of strength lost (90% down to 10%) over a decade. This can be illustrated for cumulative radiation damage of Kevlar 49 by sunlight, where residual yarn strength had been measured in textile yarn tests at the tropical test site in Innisfail, Australia and at Waltham Abbey, UK. (Figs 2 and 3). There is a good deal of scatter in individual samples, due to uneven exposure and variability of the test method. The mean values of the sets of results and the standard deviation of the control sets are shown. The weakest result shown may be optimistic. The yarn was exceedingly fragile and this data point was only obtained by measuring individual fibre strengths and then calculating the bundle strength. Inevitably any fibres too fragile to be tested were omitted.

The decay function which has been fitted to the results is that which would apply to local breaks in fibrils, supposing the incidence of breaks to increase linearly with lapsed time (t) ie mean surviving length varies inversely with time, and fibrils remain well-bonded. Thus the Cox expression for reinforcing efficiency of short elastic fibres (11) becomes

Fig 4(a) Distribution of residual yarn strengths after different times under mean stress of 2.126 GPa (b) Typical time intervals between failures at fixed stress of 2.1 GPa

Fig 5 Lifetimes measured at 65 °C. Regression and -2SE lines for means of ten.

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} = 1 - \frac{\tanh \frac{r}{t}}{\frac{r}{t}}$$

where r is inversely proportional to the radiation flux, and to the square root of the elastic modulus ratio (anisotropy) of the material. This ratio is about 100:1 for Kevlar 49. Solar energy is certainly sufficient to cause chain scission of the polymer (12) and what is to be seen in the weakest samples is the appearance of ellipsoidal voids, at least three orders larger in area than a single chain (4) but diminishing somewhat in size with depth into the fibre. There is of course nothing in the decay function used which commits it to the molecular level, and it would evidently describe random and discrete microcrack events equally well. It is also difficult to confirm the residual chain length or molecular weight in this material, but this has certainly been done for various fibres of crystalline cellulose, and the residual strength does vary in the predicted way (13).

If cumulative damage of this kind is building up under a fixed external stress, the average local stress within the material increases as total damage develops, increasing the amount of damage in an accelerating way. The lengthy integral corresponding to this process is not reproduced here, but even in the conservative case of fully redistributed load, it is dominated by a stress squared term, predicting an order of magnitude strength loss in only half a decade of time.

It is difficult to measure such changes within the spread of lifetimes in stress-rupture, but by allowing a fraction of the distribution to fail at a mean stress of 2.126 GPa and measuring and ranking the residual strengths of the remainder it was shown that the initial loss of yarn strength is detectable and abrupt. Whereas the tanh function predicts that a decade of time is needed to lose the first 10% of strength, examination of Figure 4 shows a fairly consistent initial loss of strength with time, about 16% strength loss within a quarter of a decade, to an accuracy of about 1% for the initial state. This is illustrated on Fig 3, for comparison with the tanh function. Clearly a more extensive study is needed to resolve this question, for those damage processes which can complete extinguish tensile strength.

Given the stress-rupture curve, for design purposes it would be prudent to assume a gradual loss of strength at low applied stresses, say a decade per order of magnitude, and at high stresses (greater than 0.5 UTS) about half a decade per order of magnitude of loss. It also follows that if a stress-rupture curve ever presents an order loss of strength within a decade of time, the loss may not be related to applied stress at all, but to the temperature and environment.

4 Experimental Measurements

Mechanical properties of Kevlar yarn were measured as follows:

(a) Tensile strength:

The "napkin ring" test was used, which is essentially a miniature pressure vessel. A single layer of yarn is wound uniformly around a stub of thin-walled aluminium tube to which internal pressure is applied to generate pure hoop load. The yarn dominates the burst pressure, and the technique gives high and consistent values of yarn strength, compared with other textile test methods, (5) and with NOL ring tests.

(b) Stress-rupture tests were made using a calibrated steel split ring, the imposed load depending on the opening of the initially closed ring, around which the yarn is wound on top of a PTFE substrate. This test also furnishes information on modulus and creep from the measurements of the initial and subsequent openings of the split. It follows that there is a small variation in applied load during a long-term test, which must be allowed for. The test is analogous to a lifetime test for the hoop windings of a vessel under pressure.

Residual strength prior to stress-rupture is measured by forcing open the split and measuring the changing strain in the ring. This is accurate to $\pm 2\%$, which is much less than the yarn variability in long-term tests. The loading accuracy in stress-rupture is believed to be slightly better than this. Failure time is recorded automatically as the ring springs open. This device enables many tests to be run simultaneously in a compact and reliable way, covering a range of environments. Details are given in References 8 and 14.

(c) Precise measurements ($\pm 0.001\%$ strain) of long-term creep and modulus under dry and wet conditions were obtained using metre lengths of yarn hung vertically under dead-weight loading, by measuring the relative movement of reflecting beads mounted on the yarn (10). Nominally dry tests showed a background variability from week to week of about $\pm 0.007\%$, probably associated with changes in humidity.

5 Stress-Rupture Life

The stress-rupture life of Kevlar-epoxy strands has already been reported (15) and our preliminary yarn results proved reasonably consistent with those values (10). The intrinsic variability of samples, and unquantified radiation damage to one set (15) tended to obscure the interpretation. Subsequently an empirical, polynomial fit was used to estimate the probable life of these strands and of pressure vessels (16). Our first objectives were somewhat different, to characterise the behaviour of the yarn itself, and to detect at an early stage the presence of abnormal material.

5.1 Damage Assumption

The damage which weakens the dry yarn is known to develop more quickly at elevated temperatures. We have shown above, that in terms of residual tensile strength, there is usually little difference measured in decades of life between detectable and catastrophic damage, so the first step is to predict simply the presence or absence of critical damage due to stress and temperature, rather than its exact state of propagation, or its evolutionary path. With this assumption, an Arrhenius function is sufficient to compare lifetimes at the same relative stress and then to determine long lifetimes at low stress from observed shorter lifetimes at a higher temperature. The risk in doing so is the curtailment of a predicted long life by some unknown new process which is both independent of applied stress, and less sensitive to temperature than the observed mechanisms. In the absence of hard information, this is a matter of judgment.

5.2 Molecular Assumption

The above approach alone should allow a master stress-rupture curve to be produced, but the treatment of experimental data is made simpler if the form of the stress-time relation can also be established. Bearing in mind how insensitive the strength of Kevlar is to wetting agents and to microstructure, and that chain scission is the only established mechanism by which virtually

all the fibre strength may be lost, this appears to be the appropriate process to model if a conservative estimate is to be made.

It seems unlikely that all polymer chains in the core are in perfect crystalline order. Lengths of tie molecule running obliquely from one crystallite to another will more likely be at risk, both from the concentrated loads they may carry, and from their increased chemical and thermal instability outside a perfect crystal. Kausch has explored the collective thermal breakdown of such ties (8). As in a Griffith crack, stored potential energy will be available for detaching chains ruptured by thermal fluctuation and these energy levels tend to be higher than those within a crystal. Moreover the probability of a bond reforming will be low, compared with the ideal crystalline state. The fully damaged state of the fibre core is therefore envisaged as a loose assemblage of crystallites, perhaps more sensitive to the environment than before, which can then readily slide apart.

5.3 Equivalent Degradation

It will be shown below that an Arrhenius function in log time can indeed be used to describe the time shift of stress-rupture curves with a good degree of confidence, as suggested by previous authors (15).

A minimal theoretical statement corresponding to this observation is that after lapsed time t at a given applied stress, one would expect damage proportional to $t^m \exp \frac{-E}{kT}$, for thermal excitation at temperature T with chemical processes not limited by diffusion. E is the activation energy for the process. For damage developing only linearly with time, $m = 1$. For equal degradation at two different temperatures and times

$$\ln t_2 - \ln t_1 = \frac{E}{mK} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\Delta(\ln t)}{\Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)} = \frac{E}{mK} = \frac{E_A}{K} \text{ at zero stress } (m = 1)$$

One cannot in general determine the activation energy $\frac{E}{m}$ without a knowledge of m , which is expected to change with stress level. From the discussion of residual strength above, one would expect that it might have a value of about 2 for the accelerating damage observed at the highest stresses. For a "sudden-death" model of residual strength, m is very large and the activation energy must then tend to zero at $\sigma = 1$.

5.4 Stress Dependency

Zhurkov (17) introduced the idea that delayed fracture of polymer chains under stress could be described by a simple reduction of the activation energy

$$\text{ie } \frac{E}{m} = E_A - B\sigma \quad (2)$$

where σ is the applied stress normalised with respect to the observed tensile strength, and B is expected to be a constant.

Now if $m = 1$ at $\sigma = 0$, then $E = E_A$

One should thus find for equal damage at two different stresses at the

same temperature from (1) and (2) together

$$\ln t_2 - \ln t_1 = \frac{B}{K} (\sigma_2 - \sigma_1)$$

for equal residual strengths. Since the stress-rupture curve covers many orders of time it too should have approximately a constant slope of $-B/K$. This is not what is observed when a large range of stress is considered, and we had suggested (10) that since it is the potential energy which is critical in separating a broken chain, that the activation energy might alternatively written

$$\frac{E}{m} = E_A - B\sigma^2 \quad (3)$$

and certainly stress squared - log time relations do appear to have a constant slope. Then B has the dimensions of activation volume divided by chain stiffness \times (UTS)². However, if an Arrhenius function is to be applied rigorously then B is always related to E_A

$$\text{From (2) if } m = 2 \text{ at } \sigma = 1, B = \frac{E_A}{2}$$

whereas if m is large as in a sudden-death model then $B \approx E_A$. An implication is that if the stress-rupture line were to be truly linear with σ^2 then

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1 - m^{-1}}{1 - m_0^{-1}}$$

where m_0 is the value of m at $\sigma = 1$. This forecasts the change of form of the damage growth-time law with stress.

The observed values of activation energy and slope when substituted in (2) or (3) give an apparent value of m of 2.5 for $\sigma = 1$

5.5 Reiterative Correction

The scatter of data make it difficult to determine how m might vary with stress in the interval $0 < \sigma < 1$. Moreover the exact relation between stress-rupture, damage and residual strength remains unspecified. Nevertheless we suggest taking a mean value of $m = 1.75$ to make a small correction to apparent $\frac{B}{K}$, to account for the difference between the times of equal damage (to which $\frac{K_B}{K}$ really applies) and the times of stress-rupture, which are what is observed

$$\text{Observed slope} = -\frac{B}{KT} + \frac{2.3}{m} \quad (4)$$

This correction normally tends to be within the band of material variability, but should be included in any extrapolation to high temperatures, where it will be more influential.

5.6 Data Processing

Some 370 stress-rupture data points were available at the time of writing largely from experiments at 65 °C, but in useful quantities at 110 °C and 150 °C. These were scattered with respect to log rupture time and imposed stress. Since a sample of ten yarns was the expected minimum in a test or an application, the means of strips of ten points were determined in order to treat the data. (Groups of 15 were used for 150 °C). A small correction for

creep in the split ring test was required, by taking the mean of initial and final loads. It was found that normalising with respect to tensile strength reduced the scatter of results ie at least the upper part of the stress-rupture curve was influenced by pre-existing defects. The reduction of UTS with increasing temperature is well documented. A yarn which is returned to a lower temperature is undamaged by such short exposure, so for consistency with the damage concept the tensile strength at each temperature of stress-rupture was used as the norm. The relative values are

Temperature	23 °C	65 °C	110 °C	150 °C
UTS	1.01	1.0	0.95	0.90

and the UTS at 23 °C was known for each spool. The normalised means are shown in Figs 5 and 6, using a stress-squared plot. There was no clear tendency for a curve to be formed and so a best fit straight line was computed for each temperature. There proved to be no accuracy lost by combining different spools and merges in Fig 5. When this was done, a sub-standard lot of material could be identified, with respect to the two standard errors line, as shown. The yarn tested at 110 °C and 150 °C came from a single spool of normal quality which also contributed to the 65 °C test data in an apparently typical fashion.

The mean values determined in this way display self-consistent slopes for stress-rupture at different temperatures, and so by minimising the standard error of the means, may be transposed into a single master line at 65 °C. The scatter of individual data points is displayed in Fig 7 from which it is clear that the yarn behaves consistently below 70% of UTS, but above this level there are suggestions of a bimodal distribution, which must be related to the variable behaviour of a significant fraction of the fibres in any one yarn ie a variation in the spinning or subsequent handling. If this were a delayed splitting process, it would tend to have a low activation energy and a characteristic time, almost independent of temperature.

To determine whether or not a more accurate description would be possible by rejecting the scattered high stress data, the remaining data (about eighty points for three different temperatures, which happened all to originate from a single spool) were merged to minimise the standard error (Fig 8a). The two results are compared below

	$\frac{B}{K}$	$\frac{E_A}{K}$	Min St. error	Time Shift
(i) Means only (groups of ten)	5783	9970	0.74	2.1
(ii) All data below oblique line of Fig 7	6659	10350	0.62	1.85

For prediction of long lifetimes at stresses below 70% UTS the values from (ii) are therefore preferred.

5.7 Predicted Lifetimes of Assemblies of Yarns

The activation energy term $\frac{E_A}{K}$ determined from these tests is in fair agreement with that reported previously for failure of Kevlar-epoxy strands (15) though it differs from that determined in an earlier attempt to combine the two (10).

The functions used are not believed suitable even for order of magnitude life estimates to very low residual strengths (below 10% of UTS) though it is likely they do predict the order of life at which the main drop in yarn strength

Fig 6 Applied stress squared v lifetimes at 65 °, 110 °C (means of 10) and 150 °C (means of 15). Stress normalised wrt to UTS at temperature

Fig 7 All data points transposed to 65 °C using parameters generated from means in Fig 6.

Fig 8(a) The 79 data points below 70% UTS transposed to 65 °C minimising standard error (regression and -2SE lines shown)

(b) Most probable yarn lifetimes at different temperatures v applied stress squared, relative to UTS at temperature

will occur under low applied stress. Tests still running at 20% UTS and 150 °C are tending to confirm predictions for this stress level. Note that unless screening checks are carried out and corrections applied, the usage of abnormal lots of material may lead to premature failure, possibly a decade earlier than expected.

The estimates displayed in Fig 8b are for the most probable lifetime of yarns from a typical spool, accurate to about a factor of two based on results (ii) above. Assemblies of yarns may display lives shorter than this, depending on the load-sharing rule. If failure is defined by failure of a first yarn, then an exact description of the distribution function is needed. If there is perfect load-sharing in a composite designed for the purpose, and the yarns are no longer physically distinct, then lifetime will be consistent and close to the most probable yarn value. Then if individual fibres are degraded only locally, the composite life may exceed yarn life.

For the more pessimistic case of yarns which only redistribute load once they have failed, then reasonable estimates can be made from the central part of the distribution of yarn lifetimes ie where there is a large scatter of rupture lifetimes at high stress, the loss of residual strength is sharp enough to be able to define yarns as either pristine or failed. Aging at low stresses produces more homogeneous weakening of the fibres and for a typical spool the scatter approaches the small experimental error, a reminder that the overall variability of manufactured fibre and composite will cause more serious errors unless accounted for. Gerstle and Kunz (19) discuss these problems in depth, for Kevlar pressure vessels.

The most probable yarn lifetimes projected at ambient temperature virtually coincide with the estimated 50% failure probability of pressure vessels made from a worst spool (16) particularly at high stresses, where the fibre evidently behaves more consistently when contained by the matrix.

5.8 Wet Stress-Rupture

Morgan et al (9) have aged yarns at high temperatures and 100% humidity, then assembled them into epoxy-impregnated strands and tested the residual strength of the strands. Essentially this is a measure of fibre damage. They reported a premature weakening effect due to high concentration of water. A comparison of reported times needed to develop a 60% loss of strength at temperatures of 100 °C (281 days) and 175 °C (4 days) gives an activation energy term $\left(\frac{E}{kA}\right)$ of 9,363 which is similar to the value of 10,350 for stress-free conditions inferred from dry stress-rupture experiments. This suggests that chain scission is involved in both, and leads to the suspicion that the moisture in the laboratory air, to which the yarn is exposed, may accelerate the stress-rupture. However, the partial pressure of moisture in laboratory air is only about 0.01 atmospheres, but at ambient temperatures the equilibrium moisture content of the fibre is about 3% by weight, and likely to reside in the most vulnerable parts of the fibre. The expected life for 40% strength retention at 100 °C is a projected five years dry, compared with a measured 281 days at 100% RH. This supports the view that water has some effect, but not proportional to vapour pressure.

When stress-rupture tests are conducted in water at 65 °C the short-term lives at high stress may be influenced by the water (Fig 9) but remain within the large scatter band, whereas at lower stress where lives are more consistent, there is no detectable difference, for yarn from the same spool. A plausible explanation is that contaminants which catalyse the aging are removed by immersion and that tests at 100% RH would be more severe. An alternative view

is that the wet yarn is more stable under moderate stress than it is when stress-free, as the wet creep behaviour might suggest.

Fig 9 Individual lifetimes of wet yarns at 65 °C relative to most probable lifetimes dry.

Conclusions

- 1 The tensile creep which is observed over decades in Kevlar 49 yarn under dry conditions is reversible and unrelated to the loss of strength with time. There is instead a consolidation of the normal fibre under stress, reflected in a permanent increase in elastic modulus. These effects are large enough to take account of in design.
- 2 The residual tensile strength of Kevlar appears rather insensitive to axial damage and to microstructure, but falls dramatically with increasing fracture of axial chains by radiation. This stress-free loss of residual strength has been modelled and compared with the accelerating loss of strength under external stress. Equally low strengths are determined in both processes, and there is no plateau observed.
- 3 The loss of strength under stress is temperature-sensitive and the relative slopes of stress-rupture curves also depend on temperature, so that an Arrhenius expression can be used to compare conditions of equal damage. The activation energy diminishes with increasing stress and this can be largely explained by the change of the damage growth-time relation with stress. This treatment is comparative in log time and no attempt need be made to predict absolute rates from molecular parameters. The predicted sensitivity of damage growth to applied stress persists down to 20% of UTS and possibly lower, but this depends on the fibre itself being free of internal stress.

4 Changes of lifetime with temperature are similar in dry and wet conditions supporting the view that the same mechanism is involved. Absolute lifetime at a stress of 70% of UTS is not significantly affected by water immersion, but this may be due to removal of contaminants. Further work is needed to reconcile extrapolations from high stress with those from high temperature.

5 Predictions for the most probable life of dry yarns at ambient and for dry pressure vessels made from "worst" yarn are virtually identical. Given perfect load-sharing between yarns in a composite, these yarn life values are still the more conservative. More serious, tenfold errors will arise from spool-to-spool differences in yarn strength, the variability of manufacturing processes and the poor aging characteristics of abnormal lots of material, when these are not taken fully into account.

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